

Pilot Evaluation 3: Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures

Final Version

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Summary

The aim of this pilot action was to undertake the first steps towards developing a Una Europa digital catalogue of RIs and a portal of services. The project, thus, sought to develop a platform that provided a unified system for managing RI data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities. There is a need, as expressed by stakeholders, to share information and knowledge on RIs and resources available in the Una Europa universities. This sharing is regarded as a prerequisite for facilitating cross-institutional access and R&I collaborations and is the rationale behind the pilot concept. The pilot addressed the following transformation modules: sharing infrastructure and resources, and (indirectly) comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices.

The methodology aimed to involve relevant stakeholders in specific discussion meetings. A working group of Information Technology (IT) experts of Una Europa institutions was created, and 14 participants from eight Una Europa universities were involved in four meetings, including a specific seminar to share best practices on RIs catalogues. This seminar involved guest experts who designed the Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS) that collects information on publicly funded research in Flanders, from the Flemish department of Science, Economy and Innovation.

Preliminary data on institutional RIs catalogue was collected from stakeholders to provide an overview of the different catalogues and approaches at institutional level, taking into consideration that some institutions have not yet developed such a catalogue. This overview provided a starting point from which to develop a first prototype and provided a concrete example of how a common RIs catalogue could work, whilst also illustrating the resulting benefits. Via the process of advancing the first prototype, stakeholders had an opportunity to feed into an initial discussion on the definition of a data model and to the development of governance processes so as to ensure data quality. From a technical point of view, participants discussed an approach that would avoid both the duplication of work and an increasing effort from institutions in terms of human and financial resources. The outcome was a set of preliminary recommendations for the design and development of a common catalogue based on a process of harvesting the RIs information available at the institutional level, with an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). Interoperability with existing catalogues, also at regional and national level, was discussed as a key point.

The pilot succeeded in bringing together stakeholders, and engaging RIs and IT experts, to start sharing a common vision and produce concrete recommendations for the development of a common RIs catalogue, including specific indications for universities that have not yet developed an institutional catalogue. These recommendations were condensed in a

preliminary blueprint¹. This **outcome** is of interest to different actors within and beyond the Una Europa community (researchers, RI managers, data experts, decision-makers, other universities and alliances), and provides a foundation that, with a commitment from institutional decision-makers, can be developed further.

The key medium-long term impacts are related to the concrete development of a Una Europa common RIs catalogue and portal of services (e.g., booking, training). This catalogue and portal will increase awareness among the academic and professional community of the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them. This will foster R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs that, in turn, will positively impact financial sustainability. RIs among non-academic public, private, and third sector users will also be promoted, as well as their use among citizens. Furthermore, a common catalogue and portal of services will contribute to the promotion of Open Science principles in RIs operations and activities. In general, a common catalogue can greatly benefit the academic and professional community by fostering new collaborations in R&I and education, and inducing an institutional change towards the opening and sharing of RIs across the Alliance.

In terms of **lessons learnt**, it is worth underlining the importance of: 1) sharing best practices and experiences within the Alliance, but also taking into consideration the approaches of other alliances and projects; 2) adopting a technical methodology that avoids increasing or duplicating the effort of personnel working on RIs catalogues; 3) having a clear commitment from institutional decision-makers that, in turn, will promote the active involvement of relevant professionals from the Una Europa universities; and 4) carefully assessing costs for the creation and maintenance of a common catalogue, and defining an effective management model with clear roles and responsibilities.

The key recommendation is to scale up this pilot project to produce an advanced version of the blueprint, based on a shared commitment from the governing members of the Alliance. The scaling up of the blueprint was also recommended in the Una Europa Strategy for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). The advanced blueprint will need to address technical requirements, including indications for the development of further functionalities and services, as well as a costing analysis that factors in the requirement for dedicated personnel and an associated management model.

Objectives and Aims of the pilot

The aim of this pilot action was to undertake the first steps towards developing a Una Europa digital catalogue of research infrastructures and a portal of services. The project, thus, sought to develop a platform that provided a unified system for managing research infrastructure data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities. There is a need, as expressed by stakeholders, to share information and knowledge on research infrastructures and resources available in the Una Europa universities. This sharing is regarded as a prerequisite for facilitating cross-institutional access and R&I collaborations and is the rationale behind the pilot concept. The transformation module this pilot project aimed to address is “Sharing Infrastructure and Resources”. Considering the potential benefit of a common catalogue of RIs to promote Open Science principles in RIs operations and activities, the pilot also indirectly contributed to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science

¹ The preliminary blueprint is provided in the Supporting Document accompanying this deliverable.

practices” module.

The barriers to cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration addressed by the pilot project are the following:

- The lack of mutual and up to date information on available RIs and resources. Information on the knowledge of assets, expertise, and services related to RIs is also lacking, as is an understanding of the resources available in each Una Europa university for the different disciplines. The mapping exercises carried out in the first phase of Una.Resin activity illustrated how this information needs regularly updating, and collating and updating such data is resource and time intensive.
- The lack of a unified access point for information on Una Europa RIs that can ease cross-institutional access to infrastructures.
- The lack of knowledge of Una Europa infrastructures for external users, including universities but also non-academic actors and civil society.

This pilot aims to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, Open Educational Resources (OERs), open data, etc.), whilst also encouraging an opening and sharing of RIs. In doing so, the pilot seeks to support a desired institutional change towards opening and sharing. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are:

- In the short term: Universities in general, research performing organisation, researchers, and professional staff of RIs.
- In the medium/long term: Universities in general, research performing organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaging in R&D, citizens, NGOs, and professional staff of RIs.

The beneficiaries of the pilot are as follows:

- In the short term: Researchers, RI managers, and funding officers.
- In the medium/long term: Researchers, teaching staff and students, RI managers and experts, funding and policy officers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

This pilot did not draw from any other pilots. The cooperation with the pilot action “Business-Academia Cooperation”, led by UCM, is however worth underlining; among the possible services that could be added to the prospective Una Europa catalogue and portal of RIs, there could be the link to a platform/catalogue of research teams from Una Europa universities and their transferable research results.

Initial Design and Implementation of the pilot project

The format of the pilot was initially devised during the first phase of Una.Resin activity. In this initial phase, WP2 activities focused on a threefold mapping exercise: 1) benchmarking Una Europa universities’ RIs strategies, policies, initiatives, as well as organisational and funding models; 2) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities”; and 3) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment”. This task was followed by the organisation of a co-creation workshop aimed at collecting ideas and inputs from the academic and professional community to develop a shared Una Europa strategy for sharing RIRs (D2.2), and to design and plan the WP2 pilot

actions.

One of the key inputs emerging from the mapping exercise, which was further discussed during the co-creation workshop, was the need to know the RIRs available in the Una Europa universities. Having an understanding of the available RIRs is a prerequisite to collaborate on RIs, especially if we consider that Una Europa institutions are largely comprehensive universities, which makes it difficult to have a complete and up to date overview of the infrastructures and expertise available. Mapping exercises take a lot of time and effort and require a constant update vis-à-vis the changing landscape of infrastructures and resources in universities and are therefore not the optimal instrument to give an up-to-date overview of available RIs at our universities. WP2, thus, devised a pilot to undertake the first steps towards developing common digital tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs and ease cross-institutional access, i.e., the development of a preliminary blueprint that can lay the basis for the creation of a common digital catalogue of RIs and a prospective portal of services.

A working group of IT experts of Una Europa institutions was created to undertake this pilot project. From across the eight Una Europa universities, 14 participants from eight Una Europa universities were involved and four discussion meetings were organised, including a specific seminar to share best practices on RIs catalogues. The seminar also involved guest experts from the Flemish department Science, Economy and Innovation, who designed the Flanders Research Information Space. The output from this process was the creation of a blueprint (see Annex 1) that provides guidelines for the development of an information technology platform to manage a common catalogue of RIs across the Una Europa institutions. This platform aims to provide a unified system for managing RI data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities.

The blueprint includes the following contents: 1) catalogues of infrastructures available in the Una Europa universities; 2) best practices; 3) lessons learnt from the prototype that was created to show the potentialities of a common catalogue; 4) recommendations for a future shared catalogue (architecture, system, taxonomy); 5) guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level; 6) a service portal for Una Europa infrastructures as a future improvement; and 7) next steps.

From a technical point of view, the proposed approach to the catalogue is based on harvesting the existing information in university databases on Una Europa RIs. Starting from the information available at the institutional level, the catalogue envisages an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). The rationale of this methodology is the need to reduce the level of effort for the production and maintenance of the catalogue. The document represents the outcome of the preliminary discussion carried out in the framework of Una.Resin that, in the medium-long term, could lead the Alliance to a common digital catalogue of RIs and, by extension, a portal of services.

Implementation of the pilot included the collection of data on the RIs catalogues available (if any) at institutional level, so as to have an exhaustive view on the existing tools and approaches across different universities. The data collected for this purpose were the following:

- Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs;
- Web resource/web site URL;

- Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information is stored;
- Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download); and
- Notes.

Further data (although limited) was collected to develop a prototype as a concrete example of an RIs catalogue. This allowed participants to provide input to the blueprint on the definition of a data model, as well as on the rules to ensure data quality. The data collected (through an excel file) for this purpose was as follows:

- ID: RI unique identifier in the local catalogue (mandatory);
- Host Institution: the host institution name (mandatory);
- Name: The short name of the RI (mandatory);
- Type: Equipment/Laboratory (mandatory);
- Description: RI description (mandatory);
- Location: Address, building, room where the RI is located (mandatory);
- Contact name and contact email address (mandatory);
- Acquisition year (optional);
- Free keywords (optional);
- Open access (Y/N) (optional);
- Services provided (Y/N) (optional); and
- Web site URL (optional).

The “seminar on research infrastructures catalogue: best practices”, held on the 21st of March 2023, allowed for more in-depth analysis and discussion of the experiences of UH and FUB, alongside the FRIS experience of collecting publicly-funded research information in Flanders. This specific seminar and the discussion meetings succeeded in bringing together stakeholders to start reflecting on a possible path towards a common catalogue of infrastructures, taking into consideration best practices and assessing costs and benefits.

The pilot action was planned and carried out with the contribution of the RI cluster members. The cluster members cooperated in defining the format and methodology and, in the implementation phase, consulted and involved their respective IT experts. The pilot action was then implemented via four meetings aimed to: 1) start a discussion about the common catalogue, 2) discuss the prototype, 3) explore the best practices of the catalogues available, and 4) finalise and validate the blueprint. Considering that the main focus was on technical aspects, the self-steering committees were not directly involved in this pilot action, but a prospective catalogue and portal of services will be beneficial for all Focus Areas.

The differences across the Una Europa universities in terms of RIs catalogues were a challenge in the discussions among the IT experts. Therefore, the first step was to collect data on institutional catalogues to gain an understanding of differences. The presence of universities at different stages of catalogue development, allowed experts to discuss possible common strategies within the Alliance and to think about technical solutions that could guarantee the maximum level of interoperability of each institution’s catalogue, observing what is already up and running and guiding what has to be developed. In this regard, it is important to note that UNIBO, UJ, and UP1 have not yet developed an RIs catalogue. To address this

point and make the action useful for all Una Europa institutions, the blueprint includes a chapter that offers recommendations for developing an institutional catalogue.

Different participants have different perceptions of the added value that would be gained from developing a RIs catalogue at the Alliance level. The development of a prototype was crucial to show the potential benefits of a common tool for sharing information about RIs that avoids both the duplication of work and increased human and financial resource. The opportunity to share best practices (including the case of FRIS) was highly appreciated by participants and further highlighted the added value of a common catalogue. An assessment of the added value, along with a cost-benefits analysis, needs to be taken forward if the institutional decision-makers are to endorse the continuation of this action. In this regard, it is key to continue the exchange of knowledge and best practices among experts, considering the differences across the Una Europa universities and taking into account the experiences of other universities and alliances.

Another challenge was related to the resources available in Una.Resin. Limited resources allowed for only the first step (the Blueprint) towards the medium-long term development of a common catalogue of RIs, thus raising awareness about the potential benefits and criticalities of this path. In order to see an advancement towards this goal, it is crucial to have dedicated resources.

Outcomes and Impact of the pilot project

The main outcomes of the pilot can be summarised as follows:

- Creation of a working group of RIs and IT experts who have shared information and best practices, and who have taken the first steps towards the development of a common RIs catalogue at the Alliance level. The working group has finalised a blueprint that provides concrete recommendations to guide next steps.
- The blueprint was disseminated among the Una Europa community (for example, at the Una Europa event in Leiden, June 2023 and at the final event) and external stakeholders (at the final event in Brussels, November 2023), including other European universities alliances (for example, at the joint event of the SwafS projects of the alliances on the 30th of November and the 1st of December 2023). This will allow for connection and knowledge exchange with other universities and other projects working on common catalogues. For example, the Una.Resin WP2 team met the [aUPaEU project](#) team to discuss respective approaches to the development of a common catalogue. The synergy with this project creates opportunities for exchanging knowledge and experiences on RIs.
- It is also important to mention that universities that have not yet developed a catalogue have had the opportunity to get acquainted with the systems already in use at other universities, whilst also benefiting from the specific recommendations included in Chapter 5 of the blueprint “guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level”.

The key medium-long term impacts are related to the concrete development of a Una Europa common RIs catalogue and portal of services (e.g., booking, training). This development will, first of all, increase awareness among of the academic and professional community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them. This will foster

R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs, with a positive impact on their financial sustainability. Moreover, RIs among non-academic public, private, and third sector users will be promoted, as well as their use among citizens. A common catalogue and portal of services will also contribute to the promotion of Open Science principles in RIs operation and activities. Together, these expected impacts have the potential to induce a significant institutional change towards opening and sharing RIRs across the Alliance.

The pilot project has successfully achieved its stated goals and laid the basis for promoting a barrier-free collaboration in R&I. As previously mentioned, Una.Resin has undertaken only the first steps of a longer and more articulated path that will lead towards the development of common tools (catalogue and portal of services) for sharing information on RIs. These tools can greatly benefit the academic and professional community and contribute to igniting new collaborations in R&I and education by facilitating the visibility of RIs and related expertise (within and beyond the Alliance), as well as cross-institutional access to RIs.

It is important to mention that there is a crucial synergy with the WP2 pilot action “match-making formats to improve the Una Europa research infrastructures sharing”, since the collaborative RI activities could be strongly supported and enhanced by the tools for sharing information on RIs. In general, all stakeholders involved in WP2 activities – including the One Health and Cultural Heritage self-steering committees – emphasised that having an updated landscape of the available assets and expertise is crucial to initiating collaboration. In both WP2 pilots, RIs are considered not solely a support system but also as a driving force behind research activities – a veritable “catalyser” of new ideas and scientific collaborations able to create a strong added value in R&I within the Alliance.

The outcomes of the discussions among experts and of the best practice sharing seminar are synthesised in the blueprint, an initial document that provides concrete recommendations aimed at different stakeholders. For example, the recommendations for a future common catalogue in terms of architecture, system, and taxonomy will interest IT experts of the Una Europa universities, while the next steps listed in Chapter 7 are important for institutional decision-makers. Chapter 6, on the portal of services delineating a scenario with prospective opportunities, will appeal to the academic and professional community. The structure of the document makes it easy for different stakeholders to access the recommendations relevant to their interest. In general, the document is also a good basis for exchanging knowledge with other alliances (or projects).

The outcomes of this pilot project informed the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2), where the need to develop common tools to share information and knowledge on RIs is underlined. The recommendations of D2.2 were shared with the institutional decision-makers of the Una Europa universities: the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group approved the project deliverables and recognised the importance of the Una.Resin strategies. In particular, the R&I Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 1.2) and the Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2) informed the Una Europa Vision on the transversal theme of R&I in the Una.Futura project.

In parallel, a two-phase survey was launched within the Alliance to prioritise R&I actions and allocate resources for implementation. In this framework, institutional decision makers are

evaluating the possibility of taking forward the pilot action related to the Blueprint for a common catalogue of RIs, starting from the creation of an advanced version of the Blueprint developed in Una.Resin. In the future, the outcomes of this pilot action could influence decision-makers at European level who are seeking to facilitate efforts of the alliances to build common catalogues of RIs, as an important tool to foster sharing and the opening of infrastructures and to strengthen the connection and integration of RIs in the alliances. For example, the EC could allocate dedicated funding or at least actively facilitate the exchange of experiences and best practices, as well as provide some form of coordination. This would be extremely beneficial because many alliances are proceeding separately with different approaches.

Sustainability of the pilot project

At this stage, it is still not precisely defined how and when the insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot project will be continued. In relation to a possible continuation of the Blueprint pilot, it is important to consider that this action is part of the “Una Europa Strategy and action plan on sharing RIRs” (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). In this document, the proposed action, named “Development of tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs” (see Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, Pillar 1 - Action 4), is focused on the creation of an advanced version of the blueprint towards the development of a common RIs digital catalogue and, in the longrun, a common portal including RIs and services. The priorities and actions on research and data infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 have informed the Una Europa R&I vision and are now being assessed to inform prioritisation by the governing Alliance members.

More specifically, a prioritisation exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the Alliance has been initiated in relation to potential future activities in the area of R&I. This exercise is based on a matrix of potential actions, including the priorities on infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, which will be ranked through a survey. This exercise will also define the preferred level of ambition and resources that would be allocated for the prioritised actions. The outcomes of this exercise will inform the development of a common R&I Action Plan for the Alliance. This plan will be discussed by the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group and, based on a clear agreement on the prioritised actions and resources to be committed, actions will either be implemented with institutional resources, or with institutional resources focused on attracting external funding.

The blueprint developed in Una.Resin is a preliminary step and, in order to scale up this pilot, it will be crucial that each institution recognises the added value of the action and decides to allocate adequate human and financial resources. An EC funding call to further develop this action would be needed, as well as concrete support to facilitate the exchange of knowledge across different European universities Alliances.

In terms of cost-benefit analysis, it is important to consider that engaging experts from different universities requires time and resources. Considering the differences in existing tools and approaches across the Una Europa universities, it was challenging to start working on a common vision and deliver preliminary recommendations. Producing an advanced version of the blueprint would require a clear commitment from all institutions involved. A careful assessment of the resources and cost implications related to the development, maintenance, and management of a shared RIs catalogue would also be required, taking into consideration the cost for catalogue and platform creation, continuous updating, promotion of the catalogue,

and training and assistance to users. Also, potential financial risks should be assessed such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members.

Continuing to advance the blueprint could substantially accelerate the institutional transformation towards sharing RIs and, in general, foster collaboration in R&I and education across the Alliance. The benefits of this continued advancement can be summarised as follows:

- Increased awareness of the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access.
- Promote collaboration around RIs that can stimulate new collaborative research projects as well as an efficient use of RIs.
- Connect RIs and promote Open Science principles in their operation and activities.
- Promote RIs among possible non-academic public, private, and third-sector users and also towards citizens.
- Improve the economic sustainability of the infrastructure.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

- It is crucial to share best practices, knowledge and experiences, not only within the Alliance but also taking into consideration the approaches of other alliances and projects (e.g., aUPaEu project). What is more, the EC should have a role in facilitating this process.
- Adopting a methodology (e.g., based on the harvesting of information on RIs available at institutional level) that avoids increasing or duplicating the effort required to create and maintain of a common catalogue of RIs is key. It is also important to consider the interoperability with (and among) existing catalogues.
- The creation of a common catalogue of RIs needs to be harmonised with (and become part of) the broader knowledge information systems at institutional level, and will require engaging different professionals from different divisions within universities (in particular, RI and IT experts). Having the clear commitment of institutional decision-makers (based on a clear perception of the added value) is key to proceed towards the creation of a common catalogue and portal of services.
- The assessment of costs and the need for dedicated personnel for the creation and maintenance of a common catalogue/portal is a crucial step, together with the definition of an effective management model with clear roles and responsibilities.
- It is important to consider other existing ecosystems and partnerships of the universities at the local and national level (for example, FUB is part of Berlin University Alliance), since this may impact their desire to have another catalogue of RIs shared with Una Europa partners.

Recommendations for the future

To set up the common RIs catalogue, Una Europa should ensure the following steps:

- The development of a clear commitment from the governing Alliance members thereby guaranteeing the long-term engagement of the individual institutions to work together on the development of a common catalogue of RIs, based on an accurate assessment of the resources available at institutional level.
- Continue the exploration of best practices, experiences, and approaches of other

alliances and projects to exploit possible synergies, useful tools, and lessons learnt.

- Prepare an advanced version of the blueprint (as suggested in the Una. Resin Deliverable 2.2) that should include:
 - An in-depth SWOT analysis that can help with selecting the architecture, system, and taxonomy to be adopted in the common catalogue.
 - Determining an adequate budget for the development and management of the shared RIs catalogue, which considers the costs for catalogue creation, continuous updating, promotion, and training and assistance to users. In this regard, it is important to identify potential financial risks associated with the project, such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members. It is necessary to plan how to deal with these risks and find alternative solutions to ensure the financial viability of the project.
 - Defining roles and responsibilities of the participating institutions to ensure a balanced distribution of activities and efficient management of available resources across institutions.
 - Identifying efficient processes for the systematic update of RI information through regular data collection.
 - Identification of potential services and functionalities for further development, such as:
 - Link between the RI identifier and publication/data outputs achieved by using the RI, this would also allow for a link to be created between the RI identifier and other infrastructure initiatives at different levels (e.g., European Strategy Forum on RIs-ESFRI, national, regional, institutional levels).
 - Collect the contact information of individuals requesting access to RIs.
 - Link to the registration system (to use the facility) in the RIs digital catalogue.
 - Link to a catalogue where the research teams from the Una Europa universities and their transferable research results would be available online.
 - Technical support that allows researchers to request assistance for the use of RIs and to report technical problems.
 - User training that allows researchers to access guides and useful material on the use of RIs.
 - Notification and alert system.
- Based on the advanced blueprint, the common catalogue could be created, and further functionalities and services should be developed to achieve an Una Europa shared portal of RIs services.